

1 **Nano- and rapid resolution liquid chromatography-electrospray**
2 **ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry to identify and quantify**
3 **phenolic compounds in olive oil**

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1 Abstract

2 The applicability of nano-liquid chromatography coupled to electrospray ionization-time
3 of flight-mass spectrometry (nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS) for the analysis of phenolic
4 compounds in olive oil was studied and compared with a HPLC method. After the
5 injection, the compounds were focused on a short capillary trapping column (100 μm
6 i.d., effective length 20 mm, 5 μm particle size) and then nanoLC analysis was carried
7 out in a fused silica capillary column (75 μm i.d., effective length 10 cm, 3 μm particle
8 size) packed with C18 stationary phase. The mobile phase was a mixture of water +
9 0.5% acetic acid and acetonitrile eluting at 300 nL/min in a gradient mode. Phenolic
10 compounds from different families were identified and quantified. The quality
11 parameters of the nanoLC method (linearity, limits of detection and quantification,
12 repeatability) were evaluated and compare to those obtained with HPLC. The new
13 methodology presents better sensitivity (reaching LOD values below 1 ppb) with less
14 consumption of mobile phases, but worse repeatability, especially inter-day repeatability,
15 doing more difficult to get highly accurate quantification. The results described in this
16 paper open up the application fields of this technique to cover a larger variety of
17 compounds and its advantages will make it especially useful for the analysis of samples
18 containing low concentration of phenolic compounds, as for instance, in biological
19 samples.

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2 **1 Introduction**

3 Miniaturization of analytical techniques has recently become one of the most important
4 areas of research and several groups have paid great attention to the study and
5 development of new miniaturized separation methods. Among these, nano-liquid
6 chromatography (nanoLC), firstly introduced by Karlsson and Novotny in 1988 [1], has
7 emerged as a new powerful analytical tool, complementary and/or competitive to
8 conventional HPLC, providing a wide number of important applications, especially in
9 proteomics and related fields [2-5], mainly due to the very low sample requirements.
10 Other applications of nanoLC can be also found in fields such as pharmaceutical [6],
11 environmental [7,8], and enantiomeric analysis [9,10]. The use of nanoLC for food
12 analysis has not been so widely extended so far, although in the last years some
13 interesting works have demonstrated its potential in this field [11-15]. The analyses are
14 carried out in capillaries of small internal diameter (10-100 μm), in most of the cases
15 either of fused silica or peek material and containing selected stationary phases usually
16 used in HPLC with particle sizes of 3-5 μm . In theory, by reducing the internal diameter
17 of the capillary column, better sensitivity can be achieved because the lower flow rate
18 causes a reduction of the chromatographic dilution. However, due to the low injected
19 sample volumes required in column with smaller diameter, the sensitivity will not be
20 high. The loss of sensitivity can be avoided using large volume injections with specific
21 techniques that prevent column overloading: on-column and extra column focusing
22 techniques. In the first one, solutes are dissolved in a solvent of lower eluting power
23 compared to the mobile phase [16] and the second solution consists of using a pre-
24 column combining with a switching system [11]. With both techniques large injection
25 volumes could be used, increasing the sensitivity.

1 As far as detection system is concerned, UV and, in some cases, fluorescence detection
2 are the most commonly used, although when sensitivity is of paramount importance, MS
3 detection is gaining more interest due to its easy coupling to nanoLC instrumentation.
4 For coupling nanoLC to mass spectrometry, several nanospray interfaces have been
5 tested (sheathliquid and sheathless), some of them commercially available and, in many
6 occasions, homemade [6,17].

7 Extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) is a valuable component of the traditional Mediterranean
8 diet, unique among other vegetable oils because of its fatty acid composition
9 (characterized by a high monounsaturated-to-polyunsaturated fatty acid ratio) and its
10 high concentration level of phenolic compounds. The phenolic fraction of EVOO
11 consists of a heterogeneous and very complex mixture of compounds, mainly simple
12 phenols, lignans, flavonoids and secoiridoids; every family of compounds varies in
13 chemical properties and has a particular influence on the quality of EVOO [18,19]. There
14 is evidence that phenolic compounds could play a major role in the healthy effects of
15 EVOO, besides to be responsible of its antioxidant activity and organoleptic properties.
16 Therefore, the determination of this family of compounds in olive oil is of special
17 relevance. So far, different analytical methods (gas chromatography (GC) [20], HPLC
18 [21,22], capillary electrophoresis (CE)) [23] coupled to different detectors (UV,
19 fluorescence, mass spectrometry, etc) [24] have been developed to analyze olive oil
20 phenols. However, although nanoLC have already been employed in food analysis, to the
21 best of our knowledge it has not been applied to the analysis of polyphenols.

22 The aim of this work was to test and evaluate the potentiality of nanoLC coupled with
23 mass spectrometry (ESI-TOF MS) for the analysis of phenolic compounds in olive oil.
24 When an analytical technique is applied by first time to face a particular problem, it is
25 quite interesting to compare its potential and performance with those of other techniques

1 more widely used. Therefore, a comparison between the performance of both nanoLC-
2 ESI-TOF MS and HPLC-ESI-TOF MS methodologies for the separation and
3 quantitation of this type of compounds was made.

4 5 **2 Materials and methods**

6 **2.1 Chemicals and samples**

7 Methanol and *n*-hexane of HPLC grade used during sample extraction and acetic acid
8 were purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Acetonitrile from Lab-Scan (Dublin,
9 Ireland) was used in the mobile phase for the HPLC and nanoLC analysis. Water was
10 deionized by using a Milli-Q-system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA).

11 Standards of hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, luteolin and apigenin were purchased by Sigma-
12 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and (+)-pinoselinol was acquired from Arbo Nova
13 (Turku, Finland). Other phenolic compounds used as pure standard samples, elenolic
14 acid and ligstroside aglycon, were isolated from EVOOs by semipreparative HPLC.

15 Stock solutions at concentration of 500 mg/L for each polyphenol were prepared in
16 MeOH and then serially diluted to working concentrations. For the nanoLC analysis the
17 standards were dissolved in mobile phase (water + 0.5% acetic acid) with 10% MeOH.
18 EVOO samples of three different olive fruit varieties so-called Picual, Hojiblanca and
19 Arbequina used for the study were acquired from a supermarket (Granada, Spain).

20 21 **2.2 Sample extraction**

22 The extraction procedure was based on a specific solid phase extraction (SPE) method
23 with Diol-cartridges which is used as routine extraction protocol in our research group
24 [25]. Briefly, the extraction consisted of passing through a column, previously
25 conditioned with 10 mL of methanol and 10 mL of hexane, 60 g of EVOO dissolved in

1 60 mL of hexane. After removing the non-polar fraction with 15 mL of hexane, the
2 phenolic compounds were recovered with methanol (40 mL). The final volume was dried
3 in a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 35°C and the residue was dissolved in 2
4 mL of methanol. After preparing the extracts, proper dilutions were made depending on
5 the technique used in each case (nanoLC or HPLC). For the HPLC analysis a 1:10
6 dilution in MeOH was used and for the injection into the nanoLC, the sample was
7 diluted 1:500 in mobile phase (water + 0.5% acetic acid) with 10% MeOH.

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9 **2.3 Nano- liquid chromatography analyses**

10 Experiments were performed in a commercial available instrumentation EASY-nLC™
11 (Bruker Daltonik GmbH, Bremen, Germany), composed of one module and equipped
12 with three pumps, three pressure sensors, four valves, two flowsensors, an autosampler
13 and a touchscreen.

14 The chromatographic separation was performed in a capillary column BioSphere (75 µm
15 i.d., packed length 10 cm and particle size 3 µm) packed with C18 particles. An on-line
16 C18 trapping column (BioSphere (100 µm i.d., packed length 20 mm and particle size 5
17 µm)) was used before the nanoLC column in order to achieve both pre-concentration and
18 clean up of samples.

19 Optima chromatographic conditions were achieved by using a mobile phase composed of
20 water + 0.5% acetic acid (phase A) and acetonitrile (phase B) with the following
21 gradient: 0 to 10 min, 20-33% B; 10 to 35 min, 33-40% B; 35 to 38 min, 40-95% B.

22 Finally, the B content was decreased to the initial conditions (20%) within 2 min and the
23 column rinsed with these conditions for 5 min. Before starting the following analysis the
24 pre-column and column were re-equilibrated with phase A at 6 µL/min for 2 min and 0.6
25 µL/min for 8 min, respectively. A volume of 5 µL of the sample was injected into the

1 loop and later loaded onto the pre-column using the phase A (water + 0.5% acetic acid)
2 at a flow rate of 6 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ during 1 min, to trap de compounds of interest and to clean the
3 sample. Afterwards, the valve changed position and switched the pre-column in-line with
4 the analytical column eluting the compounds of interest at a flow-rate of 300 nL/min and
5 25°C (the column was at room temperature because of the lack of thermostatzation
6 system). Figure 1 shows a schematic figure of the nanoLC system, showing the moment
7 when the sample is loading onto the pre-column using pump A.
8 All nanoLC parts were controlled by Hystar (version 3.1) software. The compounds
9 separated were analyzed with a mass spectrometry detector.

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11 **2.4 High performance liquid chromatography analyses**

12 An Agilent 1200-RRLC system (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped
13 with a vacuum degasser, autosampler, a binary pump and a UV-Vis detector was used
14 for the chromatographic determination. Polyphenolic compounds were separated by
15 using a Zorbax C18 analytical column (4.6 x 150 mm, 1.8 μm particle size) protected by
16 a guard cartridge of the same packing, operating at 30°C and a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min.
17 The mobile phases used were water with acetic acid (0.5%) (Phase A) and acetonitrile
18 (Phase B) and the solvent gradient changed according to the following conditions: 0 to
19 10 min, 5-30% B; 10 to 12 min, 30-33% B; 12 to 17 min, 33-38% B; 17 to 20 min, 38-
20 50% B; 20 to 23 min, 50-95% B. Finally, the B content was decreased to the initial
21 conditions (5%) in 2 min and the column re-equilibrated for 10 min. A volume of 10 μL
22 of the 1:10 diluted methanolic extracts of olive oil was injected. The compounds
23 separated were monitored in sequence first with DAD (240 and 280 nm) and then with a
24 mass spectrometry detector.

25

1 **2.5 Mass spectrometry**

2 The nanoLC column and the RRLC system were coupled to a Bruker Daltonik
3 microTOF mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonik, Bremen, Germany) using electrospray
4 ionization (ESI).

5 In this study the nanoLC column was interfaced to the mass spectrometry using a
6 commercial sheathless nano-spray interface with a tapered fused silica sprayer tip. The
7 key parameters of the nano-ESI were adjusted for the flow rate used (300 nL/min) to
8 achieve stable spray across the entire gradient range: pressure 0.4 bar, dry gas flow 4
9 L/min and dry gas temperature 150°C.

10 The RRLC system was coupled to the mass spectrometer using an orthogonal
11 electrospray interface (model G1607A from Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA,
12 USA). The flow rate used in the RRLC method 1.5 mL/min was too high for achieving
13 an stable electrospray ionization (ESI) (maximum flow-rate is around 1 mL/min),
14 therefore it was necessary to use a flow divisor 1:6, so the flow delivered into the mass
15 spectrometer was reduced to 0.21 mL/min. According to this inflow the ESI parameters
16 were chosen: nebulizer pressure was set at 2 bar, dry gas flow 9 L/min and dry gas
17 temperature 190°C.

18 The mass transfer parameters (radio frequencies and voltages in the different skimmers,
19 hexapoles and lenses) were similar to those previously optimized in recent works where
20 the same matrix (EVOO) was analyzed [26] acquiring spectra in the range of 50-800 m/z
21 in the negative mode. So far, nanoflow ESI has become routine in the positive ion mode
22 and just few applications have been developed in negative ion mode due to difficulties
23 with spray instability. TOF analyzers provide greatly improved mass resolution (5,000–
24 10,000 at 250 m/z) and significantly high sensitivity and accuracy when acquiring full-
25 fragment spectra. In order to obtain high mass accuracy in TOF, mass calibration is

1 required. After a good instrument calibration, the accurate mass data of the molecular
2 ions and the true isotopic pattern (TIP) can be processed by DataAnalysis 4.0 software
3 (Bruker Daltonik GmbH) which provides information of elemental composition of
4 compounds. The calibrant can either be measured within the sample itself (internal
5 calibration) or, alternatively, can be introduced externally, for instance, with a pump at
6 the beginning or at the end of the analysis (external calibration). In general, it is safest
7 and more convenient to measure the calibrant externally to avoid signal suppression and
8 contamination and to assure the calibrant signal is measured at an appropriate, controlled
9 intensity level. However, the internal calibration provides better mass accuracy (less than
10 3 ppm error). With the instrumentation used in this work for the nanoLC analysis was
11 not possible to do an external calibration because a system to introduce the calibrant at
12 the beginning or the end of the chromatographic run has not been developed yet. Instead
13 of this, an internal calibration was applied using a mixture of well-known phenols
14 present in the olive oil extracts (Table 1), giving mass peaks throughout the desired
15 range of 100-400 m/z. The seven phenolic compounds included in Table 1 (which were
16 available as pure standards) were used to calibrate every analysis. First of all, we
17 corroborated their presence in the analyzed samples (taking into account their retention
18 time, MS spectra and also by analyzing spiked samples). After their unequivocal
19 identification, we decided to use them to increase the accuracy of our results. So we
20 made an average MS spectrum of the whole chromatogram and we re-calibrated every
21 analysis by using the calibration list mentioned above. This procedure resulted in mass
22 accuracies of less than 3 ppm.

23

24 **2.6 Statistics**

1 Results of phenolic compounds are the averages of at least three repetitions (n=3), unless
2 otherwise stated. Tukey's honest significant difference multiple comparison (one-way
3 ANOVA) and Pearson's linear correlations, both at $p < 0.05$, were evaluated using
4 Statistica 6.0 (2001, StatSoft, Tulsa, OK).

5

6 **3 Results and discussion**

7 **3.1 NanoLC-ESI-TOF MS method**

8 3.1.1. Development of the method

9 In order to develop the nanoLC method for the separation of the olive oil phenolic
10 compounds, a capillary column BioSphere C18 (75 μm i.d., packed length 10 cm and
11 particle size 3 μm) coupled to a C18 trapping column BioSphere (100 μm i.d., packed
12 length 20 mm and particle size 5 μm) was used.

13 Capillary columns of 75 μm i.d. usually have an ideal injection volume of few nanoliters
14 (20-60 nL) but the use of trapping columns before the analytical column, as mentioned in
15 the introduction, allows injecting relatively high sample volumes, improving the
16 sensitivity. In the case under study, where the sample amount was not limited, 5 μL of
17 the sample was initially chosen for the injection.

18 Preliminary studies were done analyzing the best way to load the sample from the loop
19 to the pre-column in order to trap the analytes. With the instrumentation used in this
20 work the solvent used to load the samples is always phase A (in this case water + 0.5%
21 acetic acid), and it is not possible to change it. Using this solvent, an appropriate loading
22 time and speed were chosen. With a flow rate of 6 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, a very low loading time led
23 to some analytes, especially the most hydrophobic, not to reach the pre-column and to
24 keep sorbed onto the tubing connecting the loop and the pre-column. On the contrary, if
25 the time is too large, the analytes, principally the most hydrophilic was displaced from

1 the pre-column during the loading/washing phase of the analysis. Finally, the best
2 loading conditions that allowed an optimum recovery of olive oil phenols into the
3 separation columns were 6 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 1 min. This description results easier to
4 understand observing Figure 1.

5 Once optimized the loading conditions, other experimental variables affecting nanoLC
6 analysis were studied. Based on our previous studies with this type of compounds water
7 + 0.5% acetic acid and acetonitrile were selected as mobile phases and different isocratic
8 and gradient programs were tested. In general, because of the very different properties of
9 the analyzed compounds, an isocratic elution at different percentages of organic solvents
10 did not provide an appropriate separation of the selected compounds and thus, a gradient
11 elution was required. Optimum separation was achieved by using the following gradient:
12 0 to 10 min, 20-33% B; 10 to 35 min, 33-40% B; 35 to 38 min, 40-95% B. Finally, the B
13 content was decreased to the initial conditions (20%) within 2 min and the column rinsed
14 with these conditions for 5 min. As it can be observed, the gradient is limited between 20
15 and 100% of organic solvent, as in most of the nanoLC-MS systems described in
16 literature [14,27,28], in order to improve spray stability that can be an issue when
17 predominantly aqueous solvents are used (due to the high surface tension of water).

18 Different flow rates were tested: 200, 300 and 400 nL/min (the maximum flow rate
19 supported by the column is 600 nL/min). Worse efficiency and long retention times were
20 obtained when lower flow rates were used, whilst for high flows we got shorter analysis
21 time but a loss of sensitivity and resolution for some compounds. After the optimization,
22 chromatographic separations were carried out at room temperature (25°C) at a flow rate
23 of 300 nL/min . Other lower injection volumes were also tested (500 nL , 1 μL , 2 μL) but
24 the resolution did not improve and the sensitivity was lower.

1 As described in the experimental section the detection was carried out with mass
2 spectrometry (TOF) using a sheathless nano-electrospray. MS was operated in the range
3 between 50-800 m/z in negative polarity; however analyses of EVOO by nanoLC-ESI-
4 TOF MS were performed in negative ion mode and in positive ion mode. In positive ion
5 mode, in general, the profiles were worse and as far as the different families of phenolic
6 compounds are concerned, flavonoids and lignans were ionized quite properly, whilst
7 secoiridoids, simple phenols and phenolic acids (or very related compounds) were
8 detected better in negative polarity. We decided to use negative polarity for the rest of
9 the analyses. Figure 2 shows the chromatograms of the olive oil extract (Picual variety)
10 obtained by using nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS and HPLC-ESI-TOF MS. As it can be
11 observed, the nanoLC separation was successfully carried out in a relatively short time
12 (less than 30 min), comparable to some results reported in literature for olive oil phenols.
13 The resolution and efficiency for some compounds were a bit worse than in HPLC,
14 particularly at the beginning of the chromatogram where predominantly aqueous portion
15 is present.

16

17 3.1.2 Identification of the compounds under study

18 The optimized nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS method was applied for the identification and
19 quantification of phenolic compounds in different olive oil samples.

20 The identification of the compounds was easily performed by comparing both migration
21 time and MS spectral data obtained from olive oil samples and standards (commercial
22 standards or isolated compounds by HPLC), and by using the information about the
23 polarity of the compounds, the wide information previously reported in literature [26,29]
24 and the information provided by the mass spectrometer with TOF analyzer. Table 2
25 summarizes the main phenolic compounds identified in Picual EVOO by nanoLC-ESI-

1 TOF MS including information about the retention time, product ions obtained
2 spontaneously in the ionization source, m/z, molecular formula, error and sigma value.
3 As shown in Table 2 calibration error for each mass was less than 3 ppm.
4 Figure 3 shows the base peak chromatogram (BPC) obtained by the developed nanoLC-
5 ESI-TOF MS method operating at the optima conditions for the olive oil from Picual
6 variety and the extracted ions chromatograms (EICs) of the main phenolic compounds
7 identified.

8 A quite stable nanospray was obtained by using these optima conditions and, in general,
9 we could observe minimal carryover in the samples. The most hydrophilic compounds
10 (hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol) presented low efficiency and resolution, probably due to
11 the higher aqueous content used at the beginning of the gradient. We tried to improve the
12 first part of the chromatogram starting with higher organic solvent content (30 and 40%
13 ACN), but with these conditions, the resolution in the rest of the chromatogram was
14 quite worse. Compounds in the family of lignans (pinoresinol, acetoxipinoresinol and
15 syringaresinol) and flavonoids (luteolin and apigenin) were detected with very high
16 efficiency and good peak shape. Regarding secoiridoids, some of them (oleuropein
17 aglycon, ligstroside aglycon, methyl oleuropein aglycon) showed several peaks
18 corresponding to different isomeric forms some of them, previously described in
19 literature [23,26]. The extra peaks that appear in the extracted ion chromatograms of
20 tyrosol and elenolic acid correspond to the fragmentation of other compounds that elute
21 later in the chromatogram.

22 Three different varieties of olive oil (Picual, Arbequina and Hojiblanca) were analyzed
23 by using the optima conditions and the results are shown in Figure 4.
24

25 3.1.3 Analytical parameters and quantification of the compounds

1 The analytical method was then validated in terms of specificity, linearity and precision
2 for the analysis of phenolic compounds in olive oil.

3 The specificity of the method was tested by screening analysis of blank (in terms of
4 phenols) oil samples. There were no impurity peaks or contamination at the retention
5 times corresponding to the analytes. In order to obtain the calibration curves, the analyte
6 peak area was plotted versus the analyte concentration. Ten points of different
7 concentrations level ($n=10$) were chosen for the different phenols standards and for each
8 point the appropriate standard solution was injected three times. In general, wide
9 linearity ranges were observed for each analyte with reasonable linearity and correlation
10 coefficients (r^2) from 0.9670 to 0.9974. To test the sensitivity of the method, the mixture
11 of the seven compounds were diluted several times and injected into the nanoLC system.
12 The limits of detection (LODs) were determined as three times the signal to noise ratio
13 (S/N) and were ranged between very low values: 0.7 and 0.9 ppb for the flavonoids,
14 luteolin and apigenin respectively, and 30 ppb for Hydroxytyrosol. These LODs values
15 are much lower than those described in literature for the same compounds by HPLC-MS.
16 Regarding the repeatability, it was assayed out by three consecutive injections ($n = 3$) of
17 the standard mixture of phenolic compounds in the same day (intra-day repeatability)
18 and in four different days (inter-day repeatability) obtaining values of relative standard
19 deviation (RSD%) on the peak area ratio above 4.3 and 15.6%, respectively. These
20 results show fairly good intra-day repeatability but, as expected, worse inter-day
21 repeatability that could be explained by the instability of the nanospray.

22 Table 3 shows the main quality parameters of the nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS method: linear
23 range, calibration curve, correlation coefficients (r^2), limits of detection (LODs), limits
24 of quantification (LOQs) and compares them with those obtained for HPLC-ESI-TOF
25 MS. Both methods were compared taking into account the best chromatographic and

1 mass spectrometry conditions for each one. Better results were obtained using HPLC in
2 terms of linearity and repeatability, especially inter-day repeatability. However,
3 concerning the sensitivity, the nanoLC-ESI-TOF method provided a much higher S/N
4 ratio for the compounds, and therefore, a better sensitivity.

5 The described method was applied to quantify the phenolic compounds under study in 3
6 different varieties of EVOO samples. The analyses were performed in triplicate and the
7 concentration was determined using the area of each individual compound and making
8 an interpolation in the corresponding calibration curve. Table 4 present the polyphenolic
9 content found in commercial olive oils by nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS together with the
10 results obtained with HPLC-ESI-TOF MS. The variability in the phenolic content among
11 the studied varieties can be motivated by some environmental, genetic, geographical and
12 agronomic factors; all those variables have been widely studied in literature.

13 Having a look at Table 4, we can say that, in general, the results obtained for the seven
14 phenolic compounds quantified in terms of their standards in this study are in good
15 agreement when we compare nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS and HPLC-ESI-TOF MS. Only for
16 hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol - belonging to the family of simple phenols - the results
17 achieved by both techniques were not statistically the same. This fact could be explained
18 taking into account that simple phenols are the most hydrophilic compounds in the
19 extracts from olive oil and they appear in the profile when aqueous proportion is more
20 abundant in the mobile phase, resulting in poor spray stability. For the rest, nanoLC and
21 HPLC quantitative results are statistically the same, except for the luteolin content in
22 Arbequina olive oil.

23 From our point of view, it is pretty worth to highlight that as repeatability was higher in
24 HPLC, the standard deviation of HPLC results was lower. Although nanoLC quantitative
25 data were not excellent, we consider that it is very interesting the fact of evaluating that

1 technique and checking its performance and its capability to quantify accurately this kind
2 of compounds. So far, in part due to the low reproducibility of the nanospray technology,
3 nanoLC has been mainly used for qualitative analysis.

4 5 **3.2 Comparison between NanoLC and HPLC results**

6 With regards to the analytical parameters, nanoLC showed in general worse, although
7 sufficient, resolution, efficiency and repeatability compared to HPLC. However, in terms
8 of sensitivity, the LODs obtained with the nanoLC system used in this study are much
9 lower than those reported previously by using HPLC methods. This high sensitivity could
10 be explained because of the possibility to inject large volumes of samples using the on-line
11 pre-column together with the reduction of the chromatographic dilution due to the use of
12 small i.d. capillary columns [17].

13 The use of nanoLC can also offer other attractive advantages over classical HPLC. The
14 use of small amounts of stationary phases made the columns cheaper (ten-fold lower)
15 than a conventional C18 column and allows the use of expensive packing materials. In
16 nanoLC, the use of pre-columns is highly recommended, since capillaries can be easily
17 blocked at the inlet when real samples have to be analyzed. Besides, it allows samples to
18 be both pre-concentrated and partially cleaned up. It should also be indicated, that after
19 more than 500 injections of olive oil phenols, the column is still in perfect state for the
20 analysis of this type of compounds.

21 Another important advantage of this miniaturized technique is the use of relatively low
22 flow rates (40-600 nL/min depending on the column). Mobile phases, especially
23 acetonitrile, are quite expensive, and the small amount required for nanoLC makes this
24 technique very attractive with lower cost and reduction of waste solvents. Similar results
25 were obtained in both LC and nanoLC with 3000-fold reduction in reagent consumption.

1 The reduction of flow rate also allows a good coupling with MS transferring the entire
2 effluent from the column into the MS instrument, whereas with HPLC we normally need
3 a splitter. Both systems can be easily coupled to the mass spectrometer although the
4 nanoLC coupling is most delicate and present more technical problems, requiring
5 significant expertise, mainly because of the delicate plumbing and the use of fragile
6 fused-silica ESI emitters. Besides, the mass spectrometer gets dirty earlier with nanoLC
7 because the higher flows of solvents used in HPLC clean the surfaces of the equipment.
8 Due to the low consumption of mobile and stationary phases, the nanoLC method seems
9 to be cheaper than the traditional HPLC but, at the moment, because of the novelty of the
10 technique, the instrumentation and packed column for some applications are still pretty
11 expensive.

12 Other advantage of nanoLC over classical HPLC is the possibility to use low injected
13 sample volumes (20–60 nL), fact which can be very useful for applications where
14 sample availability is restricted, as for example in proteomic field. The analyst has to
15 reach always a compromise between nanoliter injection and sensitivity determination.
16 Another advantage that we can stand out is the better baseline noise, due to a reduced
17 background, which is necessary to detect minor components.

18 Tabla 5 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of the nanoLC methodologies
19 versus HPLC.

20

21 **4 Concluding remarks**

22 In this work, a nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS method has been developed to demonstrate, for the
23 first time, its application on the determination of phenolic compounds in olive oil. The
24 use and analytical performance of nanoLC were compared with a HPLC method, and
25 both of them were applied for the identification and quantification of different phenolic

1 compounds in olive oil. The most important analytical parameters of both methods
2 (linearity, calibration range, detection and quantification limit, repeatability etc) were
3 calculated to establish the comparison. The new nanoLC method provides comparable
4 analysis time and offers better sensitivity with less consumption of mobile phases;
5 however it presents worse inter-day repeatability and it can be a bit more difficult to
6 operate by the analyst.

7 NanoLC-ESI-TOF MS showed the potential to become a very promising alternative, in
8 particular, for studies where the determination of extremely low concentrations of
9 analytes is required (biological samples, for instance). Further studies are already
10 ongoing in our laboratory using nanoLC-ESI-TOF for the analysis of polyphenols in
11 biological samples.

12

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Schematic figure of the nano-LC system, showing the moment when the sample is loading onto the pre column using pump A. Valve S is switched to position 1-6 directing the flow through the loop carrying the sample onto the pre column. Valve W is set to position 1-6, because of the higher pressure drop on the analytical column the flow is directed to waste.

Figure 2. BPC (Base Peak Chromatogram) of an olive oil extract (variety Picual) using nanoLC-ESI- TOF MS (A) and comparison with the HPLC-ESI-TOF MS method (B). Chromatographic conditions are described in Materials and Methods.

Figure 3. Base peak chromatogram (BPC) achieved by nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS at the optima conditions for the variety Picual and extracted ions chromatogram (EICs) of the main phenolic compounds identified: **1**, Hydroxytyrosol; **2**, Tyrosol; **3**, Hydroxy elenolic acid; **4**, Elenolic acid; **5**, Hydroxy decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon; **6**, Decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon and hydroxy decarboxymethyl ligstroside aglycon; **7**, Syringaresinol; **8**, Luteolin; **9** Pinoresinol; **10**, Acetoxypinoresinol; **11**, Hydroxy oleuropein aglycon; **12**, Decarboxymethyl ligstroside aglycon; **13**, Apigenin; **14**, Methyl decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon, **15**, Oleuropein aglycon; **16**, Methyl oleuropein aglycon; **17**, Ligstroside aglycon.

Figure 4. Base peak chromatograms obtained by nanoLC-ESI-TOF at optima conditions for olive oils of three different varieties: a) Picual, b) Arbequina, c) Hojiblanca.

Table 1. Mass calibration matrix for internal calibration.

	Name	Formula [M-H]⁻	Theoretical Mass	Charge
1	<i>Hydroxytyrosol</i>	C ₈ H ₉ O ₃	153.05572	-1
2	<i>Tyrosol</i>	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂	137.06080	-1
3	<i>Elenolic acid</i>	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₆	241.07176	-1
4	<i>Apigenin</i>	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₅	269.04555	-1
5	<i>Luteolin</i>	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₆	285.04046	-1
6	<i>Pinoresinol</i>	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₆	357.13436	-1
7	<i>Ligstroside aglycon</i>	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₇	361.12928	-1

Table 2. Phenolic compounds identified in an olive oil extract (Picual variety) by nanoLC-ESI-TOF including: mass/charge ratio, retention time, ISCID (Internal source collision induced dissociation) fragments, molecular formula, error (ppm) and Sigma value. Internal calibration was used by using 7 well-known phenolic compounds.

m/z	Retention time (min)	Fragments	Formula [M-H] ⁻	Error	Sigma	Identified Compounds
153.0559	11.3	123	C ₈ H ₉ O ₃	-1.3	0.005	Hydroxytyrosol
137.0610	12.6		C ₈ H ₉ O ₂	-1.6	0.029	Tyrosol
257.0660	15.3	181,137	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₇	2.7	0.007	Hydroxy elenolic acid
241.0712	16.2	139	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₆	2.5	0.014	Elenolic acid
335.1141	16.8	199	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₇	-1.5	0.014	Hydroxy decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon
319.1180	17.7	183	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₆	2.2	0.022	Decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon
417.1606	18.1		C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₈	1.7	0.086	Syringaresinol
319.1185	18.6	199	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₆	0.7	0.003	Hydroxy decarboxymethyl ligstroside aglycon
285.0399	18.8		C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₆	2.1	0.018	Luteolin
357.1348	18.9		C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₆	-1.1	0.033	Pinoresinol
415.1404	19.2		C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₈	1.5	0.026	Acetoxypinoresinol
393.1203	19.3		C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₉	3.0	0.005	10-Hydroxy oleuropein aglycon
303.1244	19.6	183	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₅	-2.0	0.015	Decarboxymethyl ligstroside aglycon
269.0459	20.8		C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₅	-1.2	0.079	Apigenin
333.1339	21.1		C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₆	1.2	0.010	Methyl decarboxymethyl oleuropein aglycon
377.1256	21.5	345,307,275	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₈	-1.2	0.002	Oleuropein aglycon
391.1406	23.9	345,275	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₈	-2.0	0.016	Methyl oleuropein aglycon
361.1295	24.4	291,241	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₇	-0.5	0.012	Ligstroside aglycon

Table 3. Analytical parameters for the nanoLC and HPLC-ESI-TOF MS methods: relative standard deviation (RSD%), limit of detection (LOD) and quantitation (LOQ), linearity, calibration curves and r^2 .

Analytes		RSD%		LOD (ppb)	LOQ (ppb)	Linearity (ppm)	Calibration curves	r^2
		Intra-day	Inter-day					
<i>Hyty</i>	nanoLC	6.8	20.4	30	90	LOQ-4	$y = 887868x - 31503$	0.994
	HPLC	4.6	6.8	90	300	LOQ-50	$y = 39934x + 42004$	0.993
<i>Ty</i>	nanoLC	8.0	15.6	10	30	LOQ-2	$y = 757872x + 4292$	0.997
	HPLC	2.1	5.3	310	1030	LOQ-50	$y = 12596x + 26635$	0.991
<i>EA</i>	nanoLC	7.3	26.3	8	16	LOQ-4	$y = 1057886x + 28193$	0.982
	HPLC	3.4	7.5	1440	4800	LOQ-300	$y = 6687.8x + 76261$	0.991
<i>Pin</i>	nanoLC	8.1	16.2	1.2	3.6	LOQ-0.5	$y = 1545997x + 25558$	0.988
	HPLC	3.3	4.6	60	200	LOQ-50	$y = 37578x + 53556$	0.991
<i>Lut</i>	nanoLC	4.3	16.1	0.9	2.7	LOQ-1	$y = 3854172x + 83079$	0.980
	HPLC	2.8	5.8	20	60	LOQ-25	$y = 114566x + 59826$	0.994
<i>Apig</i>	nanoLC	9.8	18.2	0.7	2.1	LOQ-0.2	$y = 6301191x - 28625$	0.969
	HPLC	2.0	4.6	20	60	LOQ-25	$y = 150131x + 118916$	0.991
<i>Lig Agl</i>	nanoLC	9.5	22.0	2	6	LOQ-6	$y = 314076x + 405488$	0.964
	HPLC	3.0	6.7	430	1430	LOQ-300	$y = 9018.9x + 59184$	0.993

Hyty: Hydroxytyrosol; Ty: Tyrosol; EA: Elenolic acid; Pin: Pinoresinol; Lut: Luteolin; Apig: Apigenin; Lig Agl: Ligstroside aglycon.

In mass spectrometry detection limit was calculated considering $S/N=3$

Table 4. Quantitative results (mg/kg) achieved by HPLC and nanoLC-ESI-TOF MS for the three varieties of olive oil (Picual, Arbequina and Hojiblanca) included in the study.

Compounds	<i>PICUAL</i>		<i>ARBEQUINA</i>		<i>HOJIBLANCA</i>	
	nanoLC	HPLC	nanoLC	HPLC	nanoLC	HPLC
<i>Hyty</i>	30.15 ± 2.34 (b)	20.20 ± 0.77 (a)	6.15 ± 0.28 (b)	3.37 ± 0.11 (a)	21.93 ± 1.39 (b)	9.76 ± 0.34 (a)
<i>Ty</i>	15.19 ± 0.75 (a)	11.84 ± 0.56 (a)	4.65 ± 0.21 (b)	2.33 ± 0.10 (a)	13.61 ± 0.97 (b)	6.56 ± 0.17 (a)
<i>EA</i>	54.76 ± 2.54 (a)	58.18 ± 1.46 (a)	14.93 ± 1.86 (a)	10.47 ± 0.84 (a)	37.85 ± 2.33 (a)	33.00 ± 0.98 (a)
<i>Lut</i>	1.64 ± 0.12 (a)	1.84 ± 0.06 (a)	3.72 ± 0.23 (b)	4.41 ± 0.12 (a)	2.95 ± 0.28 (a)	3.29 ± 0.10 (a)
<i>Pin</i>	0.76 ± 0.10 (a)	0.77 ± 0.03 (a)	1.90 ± 0.45 (a)	2.24 ± 0.21 (a)	2.13 ± 0.31 (a)	1.86 ± 0.09 (a)
<i>Apig</i>	0.32 ± 0.06 (a)	0.43 ± 0.04 (a)	0.96 ± 0.23 (a)	1.22 ± 0.08 (a)	0.74 ± 0.06 (a)	0.99 ± 0.07 (a)
<i>Lig Agl</i>	65.5 ± 3.17 (a)	64.78 ± 1.19 (a)	20.09 ± 1.37 (a)	17.38 ± 0.32 (a)	34.77 ± 3.20 (a)	38.23 ± 0.71 (a)

Hyty: Hydroxytyrosol; Ty: Tyrosol; EA: Elenolic acid; Pin: Pinosresinol; Lut: Luteolin; Apig: Apigenin; Lig Agl: Ligstroside aglycon.

Values are given as Mean ± Standard deviation.

Means achieved by nanoLC-MS and HPLC-MS for the three varieties under study were compared. We indicated with different letters when means are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 5. Advantages and drawbacks of nanoLC (versus HPLC).

	nanoLC
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Excellent sensitivity, very low LODs (ppb) when techniques to load large sample volumes are used ▪ Small amounts of stationary phase make, in most occasions, the columns cheaper ▪ Low flow rates (40-600 nL/min): lower cost and reduction of waste solvents ▪ Good coupling with MS ▪ Low sample consumption (20-60 nL) ▪ Better baseline noise due to the reduced background ▪ Very promising alternative for biological samples
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Good intra-day repeatability but low inter-day repeatability ▪ Worse linearity ▪ Columns more easily blocked with real samples ▪ More technical problems because of the delicate plumbing and the use of fragile fused-silica ES emitters ▪ Mass spectrometry gets dirty early because of the use of lower flow rate.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

